

IMPROVING ACADEMIC SINGING PERFORMANCE SKILLS IN MUSIC EDUCATION STUDENTS

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Annotation: This thesis studies the processes of improving academic singing performance skills for students of the music education department. The theoretical and practical aspects of academic singing, its role in the educational process, and methods for developing performing skills are analyzed. The article describes innovative approaches to developing students' vocal capabilities, improving technical skills, and forming artistic creativity. The research covers singing techniques, voice control methods, and their integration into the pedagogical process. These approaches serve to improve the quality of music education and ensure the professional training of future performers.

Keywords: Music education, academic singing, performing skills, voice technique, artistic creativity, innovative approaches, pedagogical process.

Introduction

Music is a unique art that expresses the spiritual world and inner feelings of humanity. It is not only an integral part of the culture of society, but also one of the main tools in the intellectual and spiritual development of the individual. In particular, the art of academic singing is a field that requires high skill and creativity, demonstrating the unlimited possibilities of the human voice. In this direction, it is extremely important to develop students' vocal technique and artistic expressive skills.

Currently, students in the direction of music education are faced with the task of deeply mastering not only the Uzbek, but also the world musical heritage, combining it with modern performance techniques. Academic singing forms not only technical perfection, but also the student's spiritual world and passion for art. This process requires a creative approach, high skill and constant research.

This area of art turns the human voice into the most delicate and artistic means of musical expression. Therefore, in teaching and developing the art of academic singing, it is necessary to pay attention to the formation of students' personal worldview and creative thinking, along with their technical skills. This thesis considers the issues of improving students' academic singing skills, innovative pedagogical approaches and their practical application.

The methods used in the process of teaching academic singing are one of the main factors determining the quality of art education. This process requires

special approaches aimed at developing students' vocal capabilities, forming performance techniques and improving artistic expression skills. Therefore, in this study, special attention was paid to the use of innovative pedagogical technologies based on a combination of theoretical and practical methods.

Among methodological approaches, the organization of individual lessons with students occupies a leading place. Because the development of vocal technique is a process that requires an individual approach. The specific features of the vocal range, breathing technique and speech apparatus of each student are studied, and methods appropriate to their needs are used. At the same time, collective classes aimed at enriching students' musical taste and artistic outlook in vocal performance also play an important role.

During the research, the possibilities of analyzing and improving performance through modern interactive methods, for example, multimedia technologies and sound recording programs, were studied. These methods turned out to be effective not only for assessing the quality of the student's voice, but also for developing self-control skills. Also, the issues of introducing advanced methods for improving voice control and singing techniques into the educational process, based on international experience, were studied.

In addition, research-based approaches were used to guide students to creative activity and form them as performers. Conditions were created for students to understand themselves as creators, conduct in-depth musical analysis of works and give them their own interpretations. This approach forms in them not only technical skills, but also the ability to understand and feel art at a high level.

These methods opened up new opportunities for a deeper study of the pedagogical aspects of academic singing and its effective teaching. With the help of these approaches, it was possible to develop not only the technical, but also the creative potential of students.

Literature analysis (review):

Scientific literature on the development of academic singing and its integration into the educational process has rich scientific and methodological resources. The works studied in this area cover the theoretical foundations of academic singing, current issues in practice, and modern approaches. In the process of analyzing the literature, their significance in improving the quality of musical education and their contribution to research were studied.

First of all, theoretical sources on the basic principles of academic singing technique were analyzed. The studies of A. V. Yermakov and N. A. Bryusova on

the technical foundations of vocal art are noteworthy. Their works cover in detail the techniques of voice control, methods of correcting breathing, and the development of artistic expression. These works serve as an important source for improving vocal technique in the pedagogical process.

The works of Uzbek researchers on the methodology of music education, in particular T. Karimova and G. Umarova, were also studied. They highlighted the issues of using innovative pedagogical technologies in the process of music education and developed methods aimed at developing students' creative thinking skills.

Also noteworthy are the studies conducted by foreign specialists. For example, the works of K. D. McKinney and R. Stark reflect the achievements of academic singing in international experience. These studies present approaches to expanding the student's vocal range and increasing the possibilities of artistic expression in singing. These approaches allow the use of new pedagogical tools in modern music education.

The literature studied on singing technique widely considers complex approaches aimed at developing not only vocal skills, but also the student's creative potential and musical outlook. In particular, ideas on the integration of the cultural heritage of local Bakhshi-dostan and national music performance into the educational process are noteworthy.

The analysis of the literature shows that the development of academic singing requires a combination of vocal technique, artistic expression, innovative pedagogical technologies and the use of national musical heritage. Based on the experience of these studies, new approaches have been developed to train students of the music education department as highly qualified performers.

Discussion:

Academic singing is a complex but very important process that forms the creative and technical potential of students. The theoretical and practical approaches studied in the course of this study show that in order to successfully teach singing, it is necessary to use innovative pedagogical methods and develop person-oriented approaches in the educational process. Several important issues were raised during the discussion.

First, attention was paid to the role of academic singing in the educational process. Students need to achieve technical perfection, as well as master the skills of artistic expression and conveying emotions. However, in many

practices, the emphasis is on technical training, while the development of artistic thinking is neglected. This negatively affects the creative potential of students.

Secondly, the problems of voice control and the formation of breathing techniques were analyzed. Students feel the need to expand their vocal range, develop stable voice, and develop voice control skills during performance. Also, the possibilities of improving these skills by integrating national and world singing traditions into the educational process were discussed.

Thirdly, the issue of the impact of modern technologies on the educational process was considered. The use of multimedia tools, sound recording technologies, and analytical programs serves to improve students' performance skills. However, in order to effectively use these technologies, teachers and students must have the appropriate skills.

Fourthly, the role of national musical heritage in academic singing was analyzed. The level of creativity of students can be increased by introducing elements of local Bakhshi-Dostan and folk music into the vocal training process. This serves not only to develop national identity, but also musical potential in the international arena.

Thus, in teaching academic singing, it is necessary to pay attention not only to technical skills, but also to the formation of creative thinking, artistic thinking based on national and world musical culture. With the help of these approaches, students can achieve a combination of technical excellence and artistic creativity. This will form them not only as accomplished specialists in their field, but also as high-level artists.

Conclusion

Academic singing is one of the most important and responsible areas of music education. In this area, along with the development of students' technical skills, it is necessary to form artistic expression, creativity and personal voice culture in them. The approaches identified in the course of this study and the methods used in the educational process showed that they can give effective results in improving singing skills.

First of all, it was confirmed that the formation of voice technique and its proper management are the main conditions for preparing students as successful performers. Breathing techniques, exercises aimed at expanding the vocal range and enriching the timbre of the voice should be an integral part of the educational process. Also, a deep feeling for the content of artistic works and their transmission through performance will reveal the creative potential of students.

In addition, modern technologies and interactive teaching methods open up new opportunities in teaching singing. The use of multimedia tools, analysis of sound recordings and integration of international experience into the educational process can serve as an important factor in improving students' skills.

The use of national musical heritage serves not only to develop students' performing skills, but also to enrich their musical worldview. By introducing elements of Bakhshi-dostan traditions and folk music into vocal training, the opportunities for a deeper understanding of national identity and its promotion at the international level expand.

Thus, a person-oriented approach, a combination of technical excellence and artistic thinking play a key role in the development of academic singing performance. These approaches serve to improve the quality of musical education, raising the creative potential and technical skills of students to a new level. Ultimately, this process contributes not only to the development of national musical art, but also to the emergence of highly talented singers on an international scale.

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